

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the viability of river cruising activity in the Guintas River in Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo, as the basis for the tourism development framework and as one of the future community-based tourist destinations in the province of Iloilo. The independent variables are the demographic profile of the respondents, namely the type of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment. The dependent variable is the perceived viability level as a potential river cruise attraction. The result showed that the demographic profile of the respondents was a factor that significantly influenced its perceived viability level on the potential of Guintas River as a river cruise destination in the province of Iloilo. From the demographic profile of the respondents in the level of perceived viability on the potential of Guintas River as a river cruise destination, the results showed that there is a significant difference noted. This implies that the demographic profile of the respondents, namely: the type of respondents, sex, and highest educational attainment, are factors affecting its perceived viability level. Furthermore, the results indicated that the respondents believed that the potential of river cruising activities in the Guintas River is highly viable. A strategic tourism development framework was formulated based on the study's results.

Keywords: *Guintas River, Community-Based Tourism, Strategic Tourism Development Plan*

INTRODUCTION

For 25 years, the river cruise industry has rapidly grown, driven by the demand from North America and followed by more demand from Europe and the rest of the world (Bembridge, 2016). River cruise tourism has generated many impacts, especially on the economic development of many countries. Under the segment of leisure tourism, the river cruise industry has been a rapidly growing industry since 1997 (David, 2017).

According to Padohinog (2011), the Philippines has numerous remarkable and interesting river-type resorts, wherein some provide leisurely cruises. One example of a river type of resort is the Loboc River on the island of Bohol. In Panay Island, a river cruise was first introduced in the Iloilo River of Mandurriao, Iloilo City (Peconcillo, 2014), followed by the Jalaur River in Dingle, Iloilo (Marin, 2016). Meanwhile, Guinta's location in Central Panay Island made it possible for the barangay to attain a large river bank called the "Guintas River," which residents used this river as their primary source of income while local tourists visit the place to unwind (Guintas, 2021). Future community-based river cruise operation on the Guintas River has great potential because of its rich biodiversity and natural attractions that can catch tourists' interest. Nevertheless, despite the potential of Guintas River for river cruise operation wherein the community and the municipality itself could still generate outcomes, there needs to be an assessment of whether river cruise operation in the area is viable (Tolentino, 2016).

Therefore, the researchers deemed it necessary to determine the viability of river cruising activity in the Guintas River in Barangay Guintas, Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo, as a basis for the tourism development framework and one of the future community-based tourist destinations in the province of Iloilo. The significance of this study is to present a tourism development framework that will help both the local community of Guintas and the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo to formulate a tourism development plan about the potential of the area for tourism activities that will generate job opportunities for the locals and eventually will contribute to maintain and develop the economy of the municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study aimed to determine the viability of river cruising activity in the Guintas River in Brgy. Guintas, Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo, as a basis for tourism development framework and as one of the future community-based tourist destinations in the province of Iloilo. This study is a descriptive survey type of research. According to Demotillo (2003), descriptive survey design involves questions relevant to the research subject. The survey questions are then distributed to the respondents in hopes of receiving their honest responses. The independent variables are the demographic profile of the respondents, such as types of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment. The dependent variable is the perceived viability level as a potential river cruise attraction. This study's findings would be the basis for developing a tourism development framework.

Participants/Respondents. The respondents of this study were 23 employees of the municipal tourism office and tourism-related agencies of the municipality of Barotac Nuevo, 27 barangay officials and personnel, 21 stakeholders, and 326 residents of Barangay Guintas. The total computed respondents in this study are 397.

Data Collection Procedure. The researchers, with the endorsement of the research adviser, sought approval from the Municipal Mayor of the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo, and the Barangay Captain of Barangay Guintas. The researchers coordinated with the respondents and administered the questionnaires upon their approval.

Data Analysis Procedure. As soon as the questionnaires were collected, statistical software electronically processed the data. The notes from the open-ended question were collected and used to support the results of statistically driven data. Frequency count, percentage distribution, mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, and f- test (ANOVA test) was used to analyze variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings on the demographic characteristics of the respondents and the perceived viability level of Guintas River as a potential river cruise destination when taken as an entire group and grouped as to the type of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment. Mean, frequency count, percentage distribution, and standard deviation were employed. The mean is the average of all numbers and is sometimes called the arithmetic mean. Frequency count counts the number of times that each variable occurs within the sample, and the standard deviation is the distance of the score from the mean; percentage distribution is a display of data that specifies the percentage of observations that exist for each data point or grouping of data points. It is a beneficial method of expressing the relative frequency of survey responses and other data (Calmorin et al., 2007).

Table 2 shows the respondents' demographic characteristics when grouped according to the type of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment.

Table 2. The Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

PROFILES	MEAN	SD	INTERPRETATION
TYPE OF RESPONDENTS			
Residents		326	82.1
Stakeholders		21	5.3
Brgy. Officials & Personnel		27	6.8
Employees of the Municipal Tourism Office		23	5.8
SEX			
	Male	173	43.6
	Female	224	56.4
AGE			
	18-40 years old	168	42.3
	41-65 years old	229	57.7
HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT			
	Elementary level	55	13.9
	High School level	146	36.8
	College level	162	40.8
	Post Graduate degree	34	8.6

When grouped as to the type of respondents, there are three hundred twenty-six (n=326) or 82.1 % residents, twenty-one (n=21) or 5.3 % stakeholders, twenty-seven (n=27) or 6.8 % barangay officials, and twenty-three (n=23) or 5.8 % employees of the municipal tourism office and tourism-

related agencies. As to sex, there are two hundred twenty-four (n=224) or 56.4 % female and one hundred seventy-three (n=173) or 43.6 % male.

There are 168, or 42.3 %, 18-40 years old, and 229, or 57.7 %, 41-65 years old. As to the highest educational attainment, there are 55 or 13.9 % elementary graduates, 146 or 36.8 % High School graduates, 162 or 40.8 % College graduates, and 34 or 8.6 % Post Degree Graduates

Table 3 presents the perceived viability level of the respondents in Guintas River as a potential river cruise destination when taken as an entire group and grouped according to the type of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment. The results showed that when taken as an entire group, the respondents have a "Very High" perceived viability level (M=4.59, SD= 0.41). Additionally, the type of respondents; residents; stakeholders; barangay officials, and personnel have a "Very High" perceived viability level (M=5.00, SD=0.40; M=4.77, SD=0.24; and M=4.92, SD=0.11) respectively. Nevertheless, the employees of the municipal tourism office and tourism-related agencies have a "High" perceived viability level (M= 4.03, SD= 0.44).

Regarding sex, male and female respondents also have a "Very High" perceived viability level (M=4.53, SD=0.42; M=4.64, SD=0.40), respectively. In terms of age, the age group of 40 years old and below, 41 years old and above has a "Very High" perceived viability level (M=4.47, SD=0.51; M=4.69, SD=0.30), respectively. Moreover, all graduates in different levels have "Very High" perceived viability level (M=4.81, SD=0.11; M=4.61, SD= 0.35; M=4.58, SD=0.46; M=4.28, SD=0.53) respectively.

Table 3. Perceived Viability Level of the Respondents on the Potential of Guintas River as a River Cruise Destination

PROFILES	MEAN	SD	INTERPRETATION
As an entire group, 4.59		0.41	Very High
TYPE OF RESPONDENTS			
Residents	5.00	0.40	Very High
Stakeholders	4.77	0.24	Very High
Brgy. Officials & Personnel	4.92	0.11	Very High
Employees of the Municipal Tourism Office	4.03	0.44	High
SEX			
Male	4.53	0.42	Very High
Female	4.64	0.40	Very High
AGE			
18-40 years old	4.47	0.51	Very High
41-65 years old	4.69	0.30	Very High
HIGHEST EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT			
Elementary level	4.81	0.11	Very High
High School level	4.61	0.35	Very High
College level	4.58	0.46	Very High
Post Graduate degree	4.28	0.53	Very High

This section reports the inferential data and their respective analyses and interpretations. The significant difference in the perceived viability level of the respondents on the potential of Guintas River as a river cruise destination when grouped as to the type of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment. It is determined using the ANOVA test and t-test for independent samples. ANOVA test is used to compare groups to possible differences in the average of a quantitative measure. A t-test for independent samples was used to determine the significance of the differences in the intervening variables (Calmorin et al., 2007).

Table 4 presents the respondents' perceived viability level regarding the potential of Guintas River as a potential community-based river cruise destination when grouped according to the type of respondents, sex, age, and highest educational attainment.

Employing the F-test (ANOVA), there is a significant difference noted in the perceived viability level of the respondents when grouped as to the type of the respondents ($F=24.849$, $p>0.05$). Furthermore, the result in the Least Square Difference (LSD) shows that the perception of residents from stakeholders, barangay officials and personnel, and employees of the municipal tourism office and tourism-related agencies are not statistically the same. At the same time, the perception of stakeholders and barangay officials, and personnel are statistically the same. Meanwhile, the perception of the municipal tourism office employees and tourism-related agencies is different from the rest (Appendix F). This implies that the perception of employees of the municipal tourism office and tourism-related agencies is not statistically the same as the perception of residents, stakeholders, and barangay officials and personnel of Barangay Guintas, Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo. It is because of their experiences and knowledge that to view and analyze the place to determine whether it is viable for tourism-related activities. This study supports the findings of the study of Tarry & Jhangiana (2005) that experiences, attitudes, and expectations are the factors that affect the individual difference in personal perception.

Therefore, the hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of viability of river cruising activities as perceived by the respondents when grouped as to their type, was rejected.

In terms of sex, employing SPSS for the t-test shows a significant difference in the perceived viability level of the respondents when grouped as to sex ($t=2.709$, $p>0.05$). It implies that the perception of women is not statistically the same as that of men. The factors that affect individual perception are based on the mental processes that form impressions of other people and situations (Cherry, 2020). People often form impressions of other people and situations based on their observations, the context of the situation, personal traits, and past experiences (Blue, 2016).

Therefore, the hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of viability of river cruising activities as perceived by the respondents when grouped as to sex, was rejected.

In terms of age, employing SPSS for the t-test shows a significant difference in the perceived viability level of the respondents when grouped as to age ($t=4.497$, $p>0.05$). It implies that the perception of the respondents ages 18-40 years old is different from that of the respondents ages 41-65. This study supports the findings of the study of Carstensen (2015) that older adults have more positive responses in any situation because of their experiences and knowledge than younger adults with limited experiences and knowledge. In general, the younger the person, the lesser their experiences that cause a less favorable response to a given situation; the older the person, the higher their experiences cause a highly positive response to a given situation.

Therefore, the hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of viability of river cruising activities as perceived by the respondents when grouped by age, was rejected.

Furthermore, employing SPSS for F-test (ANOVA), there is a significant difference noted in the perceived viability level of the participants when grouped as to highest educational attainment ($F=12.271$, $p>0.05$). The result in the least Square Difference (LSD) shows that the perception of elementary graduates from high school, college graduates, and post-degree graduates are not statistically the same. In comparison, the perception of high school graduates and college graduates is statistically the same. Meanwhile, the perception of post-degree graduates is different from the rest (Appendix F). It implies that educational status is a socio-demographic factor that can affect a person's perception (Dindaroglu et al., 2016). This study supports the findings of the study of Mir (2014) that the primary school group was not good as university graduates and post-degree graduates in detecting or analyzing the potential of a particular place for tourism-related activities.

Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected, which states that there is no significant difference in the level of viability of river cruising activities as perceived by the respondents when grouped as to highest educational attainment.

Table 4. The difference in the Perceived Viability Level of the Respondents on the Potential of Guintas River as a River Cruise Destination when classified as Type of Respondents, Sex, Age, and Highest Educational Attainment.

Variables	Test Statistics	Test Statistics Value	p-value	Interpretation
Type of Respondents	F-test (ANOVA test)	24.849	0.000	Highly Significant
Sex	t-test	2.709	0.007	Highly Significant
Age	t-test	4.947	0.000	Highly Significant
Highest Educational Attainment	F-test (ANOVA test)	12.271	0.000	Highly Significant

The Thematic Content Analyses of this study were based on the open-ended questions which the researchers administered. This thematic content analysis was based on the theory of viability, which states to determine the assessment of the place for potential tourism activities. The researchers must gather feedback from the respondents (Aubin, 1991).

The Thematic Content Analyses of this study were assimilated with the 4Ps of marketing mix strategies such as Place, People, Product, and Promotion. This will validate some issues identified in the perceived viability level of the respondents regarding the potential of Guintas River as a potential community-based river cruise destination. This Thematic Content Analysis will serve as a basis to formulate a tourism development framework and achieve its desired objectives.

Table 5. Thematic Content Analyses for River Cruise Operation in Guintas River

THEMATIC CONTENT ANALYSES FOR RIVER CRUISE OPERATION IN THE GUINTAS RIVER	
THEME 1	Place
1.1	The viability of the place for tourism-related activities is reliant on the accessibility of transportation services in Guintas River.
1.2	The cleanliness of the area is one of the several factors that affect possible tourist receipt in the area.
THEME 2	People
2.1	Accommodation is one of the main drivers of tourism that can trigger tourists to visit the place constantly.
2.2	Safety and security of tourists based on the community attitudes are factors that can affect tourism receipt/revenue of the place.
2.3	The locals of Guintas must be well-trained and well-informed on how to properly accept and welcome tourists into their community.
THEME 3	Product

3.1	The food sector is fully acknowledged as a crucial part of tourism. The seafood products of the Guintas River can be a component to captivate tourists to pay a visit.
THEME 4	Promotion
4.1	Infrastructures – The development planning authorities are encouraged by the researchers to consider the development of infrastructures related to tourism activities, such as floating cottages with accommodating areas and holding area
4.2	River Cruise Operation – The river cruise market is considered the main focus/objective of the promotional theme in this framework because of the need to consider onshore tourism in Guintas River, which is necessary to provide a quality service to tourists and attract them at the same time.

TOURISM DEVELOPMENT FRAMEWORK ON RIVER CRUISE OPERATION IN GUINTAS BAROTAC NUEVO, ILOILO

Executive Summary

The vision of developing a highly competitive and naturally sustainable tourism industry focused on creating inclusive growth was adopted to provide the long-term implementation framework consistent with the declaration of policy set into view for Barotac Nuevo's Tourism.

The extensive discussions were also supported by a thematic content analysis based on the open-ended questionnaire assimilated with the 4P's of the marketing mix strategy that is conducted by the researchers, which essentially validated some issues identified in the perceived viability level of the respondents in the potential of Guintas River as a potential community-based river cruise destination.

This framework's primary purpose is to guide the planning development authority, specifically the municipal tourism office of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo. It is to ensure the proper layout of project development in connection with river cruises and other tourism-related activities.

This framework will secure added value/development from future investment in infrastructure and promote engagement with the development plan system to realize future opportunities. Moreover, this framework will serve as a start to the development process of the area.

Introduction

Guintas location in Central Panay Island made it possible for the barangay to attain an abundant river bank called "Guintas River" residents used this river as their primary source of income while local tourists visit the place to unwind (Guintas, 2021)

The place maintains its natural cleanliness with the aid of residents together with the programs of Barotac LGU, such as mangrove tree planting and coastal clean-up. Moreover, to ensure the cleanliness of the area, residents and the barangay officials in Guintas have a clean-up drive operation at the end of the month. The area is safe and secure for tourists since locals are law-abiding, resulting in no reported misdemeanors.

Additionally, the place is rich in seafood productions namely; oysters, mussels, crabs, and shrimp small-scale salt factory is also located in the area. However, to reach/achieve its total capacity and turn the place into a progressive and well-known tourist destination, there should be an existing tourism development plan formulated by the municipal tourism development authority of the municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo.

Objectives

This tourism development framework for River Cruise in Guintas River has the following vital objectives:

1. To set out actions to assist and promote possible cruise tourism activities in Guintas.
2. To provide a guide to the planning development authority, specifically the municipal tourism office of Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo.
3. To ensure the proper layout of project development in connection with river cruise operations and other tourism-related activities in the Guintas area.
4. To serve as a start of the development process of the area.

Figure 3. Strategic Direction Action Programs

Build-up Accessible Transportation Services:

The lack of accessible transportation services in the Guintas area might affect its possible tourist receipts once the tourism activities, precisely the river cruise operation, finally erected. The expansion of concrete roads and additional transportation services in Guintas are recommended to be pursued. Since accessible tourism enables people with access requirements, including mobility, vision, hearing, and cognitive dimensions of access, to function independently and with equity and dignity through the delivery of universally designed tourism products, services, and environments. This definition is wide-ranging for everyone, including those traveling with children, people with disabilities, and seniors (Darcy & Dickson, 2009).

The accessibility of one place is a lift for its tourism industry. Most tourists desire to go to places that are easier to travel especially tourists who are old enough but still interested. Therefore, build-up accessible transportation in preparation for a possible increase in tourist receipts once the Guintas area is fully developed into a tourism destination is vital.

Preparation for Possible Construction of Infrastructure: Planning for the possible construction of infrastructure is vital for the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo to discuss. The proposal for constructing a wharf, a river cruise with a floating restaurant, and floating cottages operation are recommended to be pursued. It is not only to develop the Guintas area into a possible tourist destination but also will probably help the municipality to increase its revenue in terms of the tourism industry.

Enhancement in Human Resources Capability and Improve the Quality of Service:

The Cruise Tourism industry brings numerous job opportunities for every individual. However, this industry opens its door to great opportunities among people in the community. Some existing human resource challenges are provoking the industry, which is significant to address. Makeshift concerns consist of a need for foreign language-speaking guides, an insufficient number of skilled workers to meet the cruise tourism industry needs lack of good training and instructors with industry experience. Short-range solutions will include providing scholarship grants to individuals pursuing tourism and cruise hospitality skills improvement programs, scholarships for foreign language learning, and opportunities for teachers to be exposed to the industry. These concerns are vital for the Municipality of Barotac Nuevo to address and provide solutions to boost the industry and academic linkages if the Guintas area develops into a tourist destination. Upgrading the delivery of cruise tourism services is a critical component of achieving a high level of competitiveness.

Adopt Measures for the Enhancement of Environmental Prevention and Climate Change

Adaptation:

Nature-based tourism can be a source of tourism assets and livelihood for the people in the community. This can also be an educational tool for highlighting environmental preservation measures and showcasing sustainable practices in caring for the natural surroundings. The Municipality of Barotac Nuevo should launch measures in this particular travel market segment to achieve a smooth sailing and nature-friendly river cruise operation in the Guintas River.

Strategic Direction Action Process

Preparation for possible tourism activities in Guintas Barotac Nuevo, Iloilo, requires effort in establishing and implementing quality standards in all possible tourism facilities and delivering possible tourism services by building its human resource.

Strategic Direction Action Process, as seen in Appendix A, has been incorporated to achieve the goal of this framework. These would involve steps in promoting the Guintas area as a possible tourist destination and enhancing environmental conservation measures.

STRATEGIC DIRECTION ACTION PROCESS FOR RIVER CRUISE OPERATION IN GUNTAS

Plans, Projects, and Programs	Target Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involve
(Place) Build-up Accessible Transportation Services			
1.1 Project Proposal for Road Widening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with MENRO that will boost improvement and enhance the transportation services of Guintas, which result to a greater accessibility of transportation. Provide detailed project proposal for the construction of road widening. 	8 months	Barotac Nuevo LGU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MENRO
1.2 Proposal for Additional Transportation Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with MENRO and LTFRB that will consider measures to improve transportation services in Guintas area. Provide detailed proposal for additional transportation services. 	5 months	Barotac Nuevo LGU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MENRO LTFRB
Plans, Projects, and Programs	Target Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involve
(Promotion) Preparation for Possible Construction of Infrastructure			
2.1 Proposal for Wharf Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with MENRO and MDRRMO that will examine the possible construction of wharf along the Guintas River. Provide detailed proposal for the construction of wharf. 	8-10 months	Barotac Nuevo LGU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MENRO MDRRMO
2.2 Proposal for River Cruise Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with Municipal Tourism Office, MENRO, and MDRRMO that will examine the possible cruise market for Guintas and identify infrastructure investment priorities for action to grow this possible market. Provide detailed project proposal for river cruise operation. 	10-12 months	Barotac Nuevo LGU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal Tourism Office MENRO MDRRMO

<p>2.3 Proposal for Floating Cottages Construction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with Municipal Tourism Office, MENRO, and MDRRMO that will focus on the possible construction of floating cottages within Guintas River and identify infrastructure investment priorities. Provide detailed project proposal for the construction of floating cottages. 	<p>10-12 months</p>	<p>Barotac Nuevo LGU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal Tourism Office MENRO MDRRMO
<p>Plans, Projects, and Programs</p>	<p>Target Activities</p>	<p>Time Frame</p>	<p>Person/s Involve</p>
<p>(Promotion) Preparation for Possible Construction of Infrastructure</p>			
<p>2.1 Proposal for Wharf Construction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with MENRO and MDRRMO that will examine the possible construction of wharf along the Guintas River. Provide detailed proposal for the construction of wharf. 	<p>8-10 months</p>	<p>Barotac Nuevo LGU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MENRO MDRRMO
<p>2.2 Proposal for River Cruise Operation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with Municipal Tourism Office, MENRO, and MDRRMO that will examine the possible cruise market for Guintas and identify infrastructure investment priorities for action to grow this possible market. Provide detailed project proposal for river cruise operation. 	<p>10-12 months</p>	<p>Barotac Nuevo LGU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal Tourism Office MENRO MDRRMO

Plans, Projects, and Programs	Target Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involve
(People) Enhancement in Human Resource Capability and Improve the Quality of Service			
3.1 Labor and Employment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working with TESDA, Hospitality Training Schools and Municipality of Barotac Nuevo to ensure the proper service rendered for the possible tourists. Hiring of well-trained employee to ensure the standard of service being offered. Community seminars to prepare locals of Guintas in accepting possible tourists and how to properly being hospitable. Imposing tariff for tricycle drivers to avoid taking advantage to the possible tourists. 	3 months	Barotac Nuevo LGU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal Tourism Office TESDA Hospitality Training Institutions Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residents in Guintas
Plans, Projects, and Programs	Target Activities	Time Frame	Person/s Involve
(Product) Adopt Measures for the Enhancement of Environmental Prevention and Climate Change Adaptation			
4.1 Preserving of Environment and Coastal area around Guintas River	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working in partnership with MDRRMO, DENR, Barangay Officials and residents of Guintas, and Municipality of Barotac Nuevo to ensure the protection of environment and maintain the cleanliness of Guintas River. Community seminars on proper solid waste management. Imposing clean-up drive operation every end of the month continuously. Proper segregation area/facility for biodegradable; non-biodegradable; and recyclable waste materials. 	2-3 months	Barotac Nuevo LGU <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MDRRMO DENR Municipal Tourism Office Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Residents of Guintas Brgy. Officials and Personnel

CONCLUSION

The result showed that the demographic profile of the respondents was as follows: The majority of the respondents were residents (n=326) of Barangay Guintas Barotac Nuevo Iloilo, most were females (n=224) with fewer males (n=173) aged 41-65 years old (n=229). Most of the respondents are college degree holders (n=162).

The result also showed that the demographic profile of the respondents was a factor that significantly influenced its perceived viability level on the potential of Guintas River as a river cruise destination in the province of Iloilo.

From the demographic profile of the respondents in the level of perceived viability on the potential of Guintas River as a river cruise destination, the results showed that there is a significant difference noted. This implies that the demographic profile of the respondents, namely: the type of respondents ($F=24.849$,

REFERENCES

- Aubin. (1991). *Viability Theory*. <https://www.link.springer.com>
- Algeo, J., & Algeo, A. (2012). *Perception: Meaning, Definition, Nature and Importance*. <https://www.yourarticlelibrary.com>
- Bembridge. (2016). *European River Cruising, Tips, Tricks, and Advice*. <https://www.z-lib.org>
- Blue. (2016). *Analysis on Mental Processes*. <https://www.arizona.edu>
- Brida, & Aguirre. (2008). *The Impacts of River Cruise Industry on Tourism Destinations*. <https://www.z-lib.org>
- Carstensen, L. L. (1995). Evidence for a life-span theory of socioemotional selectivity. *Current directions in Psychological science*, 4(5), 151-156.
- Cherry. (2020). *Person Perception Help us to form Impressions of Others*. <https://www.verywellmid.org>
- Darcy, S., & Dickson, T. J. (2009). A whole-of-life approach to tourism: The case for accessible tourism experiences. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 16(1), 32-44. David. (2017). *Global Economic Impact of River Cruise*. <https://www.z-lib.org>
- Demotillo. (2003). *Descriptive Survey Research Design*. <https://www.voxco.com>
- Diakomihalis, M., Lekakou, M., Stefanidaki, E., & Syriopoulos, T. C. (2009, April). The economic impact of the cruise industry on local communities: The case of Greece. In *CD-ROM Proceedings of the 4th International Conference of the Aegean University, "Planning for the Future-Learning from the Past: Contemporary Developments in Tourism, Travel & Hospitality* (pp. 3-5).
- Dindaroğlu, F., Özmutlu, M. K., & Işıksal, E. (2016). The effect of educational status on the perception of social and spontaneous smiles. *Turkish Journal of Orthodontics*, 29(1), 10.
- Guintas: Municipality of Barotac Nuevo, Province of Iloilo*. PhilAtlas; <https://www.philatlas.com>.
- Marin. (2016). *My Beautiful Iloilo: Dingle River Cruise*. <https://www.Iloilo-travel-guide.com>
- Martino. (2017). *Tourism Development Framework - A definition*. <https://www.germantourist.marketing>
- Murchie. (2017). *Viability Definition & Meaning*. <https://www.researchgate.com>
- Padojinog, G. G., Dolor, J. B., Garcia, M. D., Monsale, F. N., Baltazar, M. H., Jolito, E. B., ... & Savillo, I. T. (2011). The potential of Tinorian River as an eco-tourism spot in the Province of Iloilo, Philippines. *Journal of Wetlands Ecology*, 5, 79-82.
- Paler-Calmorin, L., & Calmorin, M. A. (2007). *Research methods and thesis writing*. Rex Book Store.
- Peconcillo. (2014). *Iloilo River Cruise via Solar Boat*. <https://www.Iloilo-travel-guide.com>
- Sugaya. (2003). *THL Tourism Site Assessment Tool*. Tibetan and Himalaya Library. <https://www.goodfellowpublisher.com>

Tarry, & Jhiangana. (2005). *Principles of Social Psychology Individual Differences in Person Perception*. Cambridge University Press.

Tolentino. (2020). *The Viability of Tourism Destination*. <https://www.Iloilo-travel-guide.com>

Turner, J. R., Turner, J. R., & Turner, T. (1999). *The handbook of project-based management: improving the processes for achieving strategic objectives*.

Turner, R. K. (1993). *Sustainable environmental economics and management: principles and practice*. Belhaven Press.

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